

The Study of University Teacher's Value upon their Job

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study was to examine the value of university teacher upon the job. The questionnaires used in this research were developed by Psychology Department in Dagon University. The questionnaire consists of four categories: motivation, duty consciousness, job stress and job satisfaction. In this research, 100 teachers from universities were used as respondents, thirty four percent are males and sixty-six percent females. Data were collected by administering a survey questionnaire comprising 32 items. The findings were described in percentage. The findings showed that level of motivation, duty consciousness and job satisfaction of university teachers were high and only little of teachers having stress in their profession.

Introduction

This study aims to explore the value of teachers from universities. Values represent basic convictions that "a specific mode of conduct or end-state of existence is personally or socially preferable to an opposite or converse mode of conduct or end-state of existence". They contain a judgmental element in that they carry an individual's idea as to what is right, good, or desirable. Values are important to the study of organizational behavior because they lay the foundation for the understanding of attitude and motivation and because they influence people's perception.

Attitudes are evaluative statements or adjustments— either favourable or unfavourable— concerning objects, people, or events. Attitudes are not the same as value, but the two are intercorrelated.

Motivation is the result of the interaction of the individual and the situation. Certainly, individuals differ in their basic motivational drive. Motivation is the willingness to exert high levels of effort toward organizational goals, conditioned by the individual's ability to satisfy some individual needs. The motivated employees are in a state of tension, and they exert effort. The greater the tensions, the higher the effort level. If this effort successfully leads to the satisfaction of the needs, tension is reduced. This tension reduction effort must also be directed toward organizational goals.

Stress is a dynamic condition in which an individual is confronted with a constraint, or demands related to what he or she desires and for which the outcome is perceived to be both uncertain and important. Stress is associated with constraints and demands. The former prevents you from what you desire. The latter refers to the loss of something desired. Stress is the highest for those individuals who perceive that they are uncertain as to whether they will win or lose and the lowest for those individuals who think that winning or losing is certain. But importance is also critical. If winning or losing is an unimportant outcome, there is no stress.

Job satisfaction refers to an individual's general attitude toward his or her job. A person with a high level of job satisfaction holds positive attitudes toward the job, while a person who is dissatisfied with his or her job holds negative attitudes about the job. The dissatisfied employees skip work more often and are more likely to resign. Satisfied employees have better health and live longer. An employee who has satisfaction on the job carries over to the employee's life outside the job.

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Since the value of teachers influence the individuals and organizations, we have to explore the values of teachers from universities.

Materials and Methods

- Objectives : 1. To explore the university teacher's motivation.
2. To examine the university teacher's duty consciousness.
3. To explicit the university teacher's job stress.
4. To find out the university teacher's job satisfaction.
- Hypothesis : University teacher's motivation on their job is high.
Duty consciousness of university teacher's is high.
Level of job stress is low.
Most of the university teachers have satisfaction of their job.
- Sample : Hundred university teachers, thirty-four males and sixty-six females, were used as subjects. These university teachers were from Dagon University, University of Yangon, West Yangon University, East Yangon University and University of Economics. The subjects were from tutors, demonstrators to associate professors.
- Instruments : In this research, thirty-two questionnaires were used to study the university teacher's values on the job. The questions were classified into four categories. These were motivation, duty consciousness, job stress, and job satisfaction.
- Procedures : Teachers from universities were firstly approached and asked to complete survey questionnaires. Then thirty-two questionnaires of four categories were administered to teachers from universities in Yangon Region. Respondents were asked to report their responses as true (Ā) for favourable and false (â) for unfavourable. Then the answers, true or false, were collected and scored (1) for true and (0) for false.

Result and Discussion

According to the objectives of this study, value of university teachers on their profession were examined. Thirty-two questionnaires of four categories were administered to the 100 university teachers, thirty-four males and sixty-six females.

Table 1. Percentage of Responses on Motivation

Number of cases	High motivation (%)	Low motivation (%)
100	80	20

Table 1 showed the motivation of university teachers. The majority of teachers, 80%, had high motivation on their profession. They were very enthusiastic about their job. They always make preparation for their profession. Problems in workplace were overcome. They

always pay full attention to their job which was done on time. Teachers were interested in teaching, other administrative duties in workplace and social activities every day. They always have objectives whatever they do.

A few of teachers, 20%, who were low in motivation in their profession. They only did regularly with low enthusiasm in their work. They did not make any preparation for daily duty. If they encountered a problem in workplace, they felt stressed easily. They always think to transfer to another job which is better than the present job. They had no plan and no objectives for their profession.

Table 2. The Level of Duty Consciousness

Number of cases	High duty consciousness (%)	Low duty consciousness (%)
100	88	12

Table 2 indicates the level of duty conscious on the profession. Eighty-eight percentage of university teachers were high in duty conscious on their job. They take care of health, so that they will not be absent in their job. They are always worried that they do not complete their work in time. They did not want absenteeism from their workplace.

Only twelve percent of university teachers were low in duty consciousness. They never had worries about completing their work in time. They did not take care of health, so they were always absent from their job.

Table 3. Percentage of Responses on Job Stress

Number of cases	Low stress (%)	Stress (%)
100	85	15

Table 3 presents that only a few percentages of teachers who accepted the jobs which was giving stress to them. They felt stressed in doing extra duty besides teaching. The problems in working situation were disappointing for them. Many duties done at the work in time caused their stress. They felt that there were not balances in workload and capacity. So, if possible, they would like to shift another profession.

But many university teachers, eighty-five percentage, had low level of stress in their profession. They always expected the problems and difficulties in working situation and performing so many duties at work caused them to get experiences as they accepted. They also believed that many stress might be encountered in every work and they prepared to overcome these stress.

Table 4. Percentage of Responses on Job Satisfaction

Number of cases	Satisfaction (%)	Unsatisfaction (%)
100	90	10

Table 4 indicates the percentage of responses by university teachers who had satisfaction or unsatisfaction on their professional work. Ninety percent of teachers responded that they were working happily in the job. They felt that performing this profession fulfilled life pleasure in their mind, as they were happy in working situation and they were full of satisfaction in their life. They were proud of working as university teachers and worked hard forever.

Only ten percentages of teachers who felt unhappy, unsatisfied, and stressed in working in this profession was observed. They did not realize that doing different duties gave them new experiences. They assumed that working different duties were heavy workload for them. They also felt that friends in workplace did not give warmth to them.

Conclusion

Teachers from universities in Yangon Region were most likely to prefer performing as university teachers. According to the data, majority of university teachers, eighty percent, were high in motivation. They were very willingly to do their job, doing preparation, overcoming the problems at work, and to pay full attention to the job, whatever they did with objectives.

Teachers have also high duty consciousness. They never want to be absent and to have unfinished work in time. They always take care of their health, not to be absent from the job.

Most of university teachers expected the problems and difficulties in working situation. They also believe that doing different duties at work caused them to get new experiences. A little university teachers, fifteen percentages, felt that there were no balance in loading and capacities. Different duties done at work in time caused them stress.

Majority of teachers felt satisfaction in doing this profession. They were proud of working as university teachers and so worked hard forever. Performing this profession, they felt fulfilled life, pleasure in their mind and were full of satisfaction in life.

The result of the study shows that most of university teachers were high in motivation, duty consciousness, job satisfaction and low in job stress. The findings from this study suggested that teachers from universities have positive values on their job.

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